

**BASIC LITERARY ELEMENTS OF THE XX CENTURY ENGLISH
AND UZBEK SHORT STORIES (BASED ON HERBERT BATES
AND SAID AHMAD'S SHORT STORIES)**

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Annotation: The story is a small epic genre in artistic literature, a composed prose piece of life. The story of world literature has ancient traditions. In the past, the story took part in the composition of folklore works. As an independent genre, it is only in written literature. Over the last one hundred and fifty years, the short story has gained popularity in the literature of several countries. Although short story is the most widely read of all the genres in the modern times, yet little critical attention is given to the short story. Short Story saw a temporary setback in the forties owing to interruption made by the war and the literary energies was scattered into different fields. Nevertheless, a few short stories were inspired by war of which the excellent were by H. E. Bates: which appeared under the Pseudonym of “Flying officer X”. Bates first collection “The Greatest people in the world” “sold like hot cakes and a little above three hundred thousand copies were sold. Another factor responsible for scanty output in the body of the Short story was due to paper shortage. The problem was overcome a little soon before the rise of the next decade.

Herbert Ernest Bates is widely recognized as one of the finest short story writers of his generation, with more than 20 story collections published in his lifetime. It should not be overlooked, however, that he also wrote some outstanding novels, starting with “The Two Sisters” through to “A Moment in Time”.

In Uzbek literature story genre appeared very long years ago. Nosiriddin Rabg‘uziy’s collection “Kissai Rabg‘uziy” also includes different kinds of ethical stories. The works of Sufi Alloyor “Sabot ul-aljizin” and Mashrab’s “Mabdai Nur”

include more than hundreds of “hikoyats” in verse. There are many examples of hikoyats in Alisher Navoi’s “Khamsa”.

Alisher Navoiy’s doston “Hayrat ul-abror” includes “Hotami Toy hikoyat”, “Ul qul hikoyat”, and another Navoi’s doston “Sab’ai sayyor” includes “Yeti musofir hikoyat”. [2;23]

The short story today is the most popular of literary forms and the short story writer continues to project life with its beauty and ugliness, with its philosophy and realism and with a stress on individual experience and individual vision. It continues to discover “the unity of the individual” behind the multiplicity of its living. It should be noted that Uzbek writer Said Ahmad made a worthy contribution to the development of Uzbek short story genre. His dozens of stories such as ““Cho’l burguti” (The Desert Eagle), “O’rik dolma”(An Apricot teacher),” Lochin”(Falcon), “Khazina” (Treasure), “Haykyriq”(Scream) took the great place in our literature. Bates for all his originality is remarkably similar to Russian writer Chekhov, whom he honored and whom he studied. An English writer took from Chekhov not only the plots but also the principles of constructing the story, an aesthetic standard. They both have the same preferences, philosophy, themes, equally subtle as if in half tones, style.

Philosophy and similar themes are seen in H.Bates and Said Ahmad’s stories. We have analyzed many stories of both writers from different poin. Let’s analyze the beginning of the story “Time” by Herbert Bates and “Cranes ” by Said Ahmad where both authors lively described the nature of the country.

Said Ahmad stands the second in the list of Uzbek master of storywriters after Abdulla Kahhar. “Turnalar” (Cranes) is one of his best stories. The image of Sobirzhon stands in the center of the story who had two sons. His both sons died in the war. Then he adopted one boy but he also found his siblings and left him.

The stories with moral ideas are very similar with each other. Let us see the beginning of these stories, where both writers started them with the description of nature.

“Time”by H. Bates	“Turnalar” (Cranes) by Said Ahmad
Sitting on an iron seat fixed about the body of a great chestnut tree breaking into pink-flushed blossom, two old men gazed dumbly at the sunlit emptiness of a town square. The morning sunburned in a sky of marvelous blue serenity, making the drooping leaves of the tree most brilliant and the pale blossoms expand to fullest beauty	Tepalikdan oshib o‘tganimdan keyingina anhorning guvillashi eshitilmay qoldi. Dala jimjit. Shamol ananas hidini olib keladi. Qaerdandir, yaqinginadan turnaning qure-quresi eshitiladi. Bu ovoz negadir osmondan emas, pastdan kelardi.

The rural English life and even the English nature itself was the leading theme of many of Bates’ works. He believed that nature in his wealth and inflexibility has a dual impact on the lives of people close to him. The writer recalled that he was most of all responsible for his upbringing on his maternal grandfather, who had already left a shoemaker as an elderly person and started gardening and gardening. Most works of Said Ahmad are named and connecting with nature. For example “Bo‘ston” (Blooming garden), “Yer uyg‘ondi”, The Awakening), “Qishdan qolgan qarg‘alar” (Winter hawks), “To‘lqinlar”(Waves), “Yalpiz hidi” (Mint smell), “Tog‘afsonasi”(Myth of the mountain) and so on. According to a well-known Uzbek writer, Utkir Hoshimov’s notes about Said Ahmad that the writer had a very big garden with many fruit trees. This love to the nature is seen in the works of these writers.

The stories of Herbert Bates and Said Ahmad are moralistic and very similar with each other. The readers of each nation read their stories with pleasure as the description of nature, social life of people and rural life are given accurately in both of them.

The list of used literature:

1. Baldwin, D. (1993). The tardy evolution of the British short story. Studies In Short Fiction
2. Kamilova S.E. Genre Transformation of a Short-Story in the Late XX – Early XXI Centuries in Russian and Uzbek Literature.-p3
3. Said Ahmad.Ta'zim. «Toshkent» badiiy adabiyot nashriyoti. 1966.-p63
4. <https://www.thefamouspeople.com/profiles/herbert-ernest-bates-1557.php>